

DESIGN OF SEMI-COMPLEX PARTS USING ANISOTROPIC CARBON FIBER CARD WEB REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

The lightness of vehicles is important to realize the high fuel efficiency and reduction of energy consumption. CFRP is expected to replace iron as main material for vehicle body. In this study, we focus on CWT (Carbon fiber card Web reinforced Thermoplastics) materials which have advantages of recycling, mechanical property and formability. The purpose of this research is to propose that optimum mechanical properties can be given to semi-complex structures by using the anisotropy of CWT material. In this study, it was first verified that the mechanical properties of CWT can be calculated from the fiber orientation distribution (FOD) by Netting Theory. Next, we performed functional fitting of FOD data and prepared for mechanical property optimization by FEM analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growth of world total fossil energy consumption is partly led by the increase of the energy consumed in the transport sector [1]. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have developed the weight saving of parts such as aerospace [2] and pressure vessel so far. In recent years it is strongly desired to apply it to semi-complex shaped and small parts such as automotive and drone to realize the low-carbon society.

Structure require that their material have enough strength and stiffness in specific direction. If we use anisotropic materials, we can get ideal materials which have enough strength and stiffness in specific direction. This means that we can make a design with optimal weight of material. It can lead saving weights and materials.

Composite materials like CFRP are heterogeneous materials and they have anisotropic properties. But conventional CFRP achieve ideal isomerization by complex lamination of sheets which is composed carbon fiber in uni-direction and resin. This complex manufacturing process and the weakness of interlaminar strength cause negative effect to anisotropic CFRP materials. Compared to these CFRP material, the anisotropic properties of CWT material can be controlled by changing the ratio of longitude and transverse fibers without complex lamination and problem of delamination.

2 MATERIALS

In this study, a novel CFRP material called carbon fiber card web reinforced thermoplastics (CWT) from Ehime Institute of Industrial Technology Paper Technology Center in Japan is focused. This material is manufactured by a non-woven carding machine (SSRC-420, Figure 1), which is composed of the needles of interactive perpendicular movements with a belt of unidirectional movement. In this process, carbon fibers (length: 53 mm, T-700, Toray product) and resin fibers (length: 51mm, PA6, UNITIKA product) are mixed together and non-woven fabric of carbon and resin fibers can be made. CWT can use not only virgin carbon fibers but also recycled carbon fibers, so it is expected that CWT can be the solution of recycling CFRP.

And CWT can be created by laminating CWT sheets and heating-pressing with a press machine. When a 250*120*2 mm plate is prepared, about 90 g CWT sheets are laminated (Figure 2) and heated and pressurized at 280 ° C. and 7 MPa.

The orientation of the contained carbon fibers can be changed by stretching the CWT sheet before laminating. This change rate is called Stretch ratio and is written as $S\circ$. Hereinafter, $S20_CWT30\%$ means that it is a CWT (V_f : 30%) manufactured from a CWT sheet whose Stretch ratio is 20%.

Figure 1 non-woven carding machine.

Figure 2 CWT sheets.

3 THE VALIDITY OF NETTING THEORY

According to Netting Theory [3, 4], the property of composite materials can be calculated from fiber volume fraction (V_f) and fiber orientation distribution (FOD) (Eq. (1) to (7)). $f(\theta)$ stands for probability of fiber orientation distribution. E_f is elastic modulus of carbon fiber.

$$\int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} f(\theta) d\theta = 1 \quad \left(-\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$E_{11} = E_f V_f \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos^4 \theta f(\theta) d\theta \quad (2)$$

$$E_{22} = E_f V_f \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^4 \theta f(\theta) d\theta \quad (3)$$

$$E_{12} = E_f V_f \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos^2 \theta \cdot \sin^2 \theta f(\theta) d\theta \quad (4)$$

$$E_L = E_{11} - \left(\frac{E_{12}^2}{E_{22}}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$E_T = E_{22} - \left(\frac{E_{12}^2}{E_{11}}\right) \quad (6)$$

$$G_{LT} = E_{12} \quad (7)$$

The FOD were measured by using the X-ray micro-CT analysis [5]. Figure 3 shows the mechanism of X-ray micro-CT. The micro-CT scans the image of specimen and performs image processing. Figure 4 shows a sample of FOD from X-ray micro-CT.

Figure 3 Schematic of scanning process [5].

Figure 4 A sample of FOD.

In order to verify the validity of the Netting Theory, CWT specimens were prepared and mechanical property tests were conducted. And we compare the results with the predictions calculated from the FOD (Figure 5). This graph shows us that Netting Theory can apply to the prediction of CWT mechanical property.

Figure 5 Comparison of experiment results and predict results from Netting Theory.

4 SIMULATION

4.1 FUNCTIONALIZATION OF FIBER ORIENTATION DISTRIBUTION (FOD)

The FOD data is approximated to be easy to handle. The fiber orientation distribution appears to occur essentially randomly. Therefore, it was thought that FOD data could be functionalized by superimposing a normal distribution. In addition, FOD data obtained by micro-CT image processing was averaged so as to be symmetrical around 90 degrees.

As a feature of CWT FOD data, a large peak exists at 0, 180 degrees and 90 degrees. Therefore, the sizes and variances of the two peaks are represented by four variables in total. We also added a constant term to represent the overall variability.

$$f(\theta) = a \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{0,180}^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\theta^2}{2\sigma_{0,180}^2}\right) + b \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{90}^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\theta - 90)^2}{2\sigma_{90}^2}\right) + a \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{0,180}^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\theta - 180)^2}{2\sigma_{0,180}^2}\right) + c$$

a, b represent the peak size, and σ represents the variance. In this study, 4 FOD data were approximated using this function. The 4 FOD data were obtained by micro-CT, and the data were averaged to be symmetric about 90 degrees. These data are for V_f 30% and 40%, and two different stretch ratios. Fitting was performed using Excel's solver, changing five parameters of the function, and calculating so that the sum of squares of differences between FOD data and function values was minimized. The following result (Figure 6, 7, and Table 1, 2) is obtained when this function is approximated by averaged FOD data measured by micro-CT.

Figure 6 Comparison of fitted function and averaged FOD data (V_f 30%).

Table 1 numerical value of parameter of fitting function (V_f 30%).

	$\sigma_{0,180}$	a	σ_{90}	b	c
S0_30%	83.198	89.815	0.129	14.480	0.607
S30_30%	70.900	110.285	0.118	11.725	0.406

Figure 7 Comparison of fitted function and averaged FOD data (V_f 40%).

Table 2 numerical value of parameter of fitting function (V_f 40%).

	$\sigma_{0,180}$	a	σ_{90}	b	c
S0_40%	152.608	63.541	0.122	12.380	0.483
S48_40%	218.030	73.310	0.134	13.501	0.318

4.2 MODELING

The hat-shaped structure was used as a model of the semi-complex structure, and the optimization of mechanical properties was verified. The hat model has dimensions as shown below (Figure 8,9). The mechanical property uses that which are obtained by interpolating and extrapolating a fictional mechanical property from what was functioned by 4.1. In addition, the simulation performs a 3-point bending test of the hat structure, and calculates the elastic modulus of the structure from its load and displacement. By this simulation, it is possible to find the optimum mechanical characteristics for the bending of the hat structure. Since the calculation is currently underway, the calculation results will be presented on the ICCM 22.

Figure 8 Scale of a hat-shaped structure.

Figure 9 FEM model of hat-shaped structure

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to optimize CWT mechanical properties for quasi-complex structures. From the research so far, it has been found that the mechanical properties of CWT can be calculated from FOD data by applying Netting Theory. The shear modulus and strength need to be studied in more detail.

Moreover, it turned out that FOD data can be approximated by superposition of normal distribution. Although FOD changes with the change of Stretch ratio, it turned out that the FOD is possible to be expressed using five parameters.

From now on, it is possible to optimize, by using the created FEM model, FOD and mechanical property of CWT by changing the five parameters. This enables more efficient determination of mechanical properties and design, leading to the spread of CWT materials.

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